

Reactions of Ferric Isopropoxide with Organic Esters

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Although ferric ethoxide was prepared by Thiessen and Koerner¹ in 1929, yet it is only during the past fifteen years that some efforts have been directed towards a systematic investigation of iron alkoxides, in general. Particularly important has been the work of Bradley, Multani and Wardlaw². Further interest in this field has been stimulated by the studies of Martin, Winter and co-workers^{3,4}.

For the first time, Baker⁵ employed the transesterification reactions for the synthesis of higher alkoxides from the lower aluminium alkoxides. These have been recently found to be of great practical utility in the preparation of tertiary alkoxides⁶ of zirconium and hafnium which could not be prepared by alternative methods in reasonably good yields. The method has been extended to the preparation of alkoxides of a number of metals Al⁷, V⁸, Nb⁹, Ta¹⁰, Sn¹¹ by Mehrotra and co-workers.

Reactions of ferric isopropoxide with a number of organic esters, i.e., *n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl, *sec*-butyl, *tert*-butyl, *n*-pentyl and phenylacetates have been carried out by the authors and higher alkoxides of iron were isolated in quantitative yields.

$$\text{Fe}(\text{OPr}^i)_3 + 3\text{RCOOCH}_3 \longrightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{OR})_3 + 3\text{CH}_3\text{COOPr}^i$$
 (where R=*n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl, *sec*-butyl, *tert*-butyl, *n*-pentyl and phenyl groups).

In some of the above reactions, ferric isopropoxide was dissolved in the excess of the organic ester and the solution was refluxed under a fractionating column. The lower boiling isopropyl acetate produced in the reaction was slowly fractionated till the temperature rose upto the boiling point of the ester added. The product was then volatilised under reduced pressure.

In the case of higher boiling esters, an inert solvent like cyclohexane was used as suggested by Mehrotra and Kapoor^{9,10} which forms an azeotrope with isopropyl acetate liberated during the reaction. Two probable mechanisms for transesterification reactions¹² have

1. P. A. Thiessen and O. Koerner, *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1929, **180**, 65; 1930, **191**, 74.
2. D. C. Bradley, R. K. Multani and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 126; *ibid.*, 1958, 4153.
3. R. L. Martin, G. Winter, R. W. Adams and C. G. Barraclough, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 346.
4. R. L. Martin, G. Winter and R. W. Adams, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 207, 363.
5. R. H. Baker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2673.
6. R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2266.
7. R. C. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 585.
8. R. K. Mittal, and R. C. Mehrotra, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1964, **327**, 311.
9. P. N. Kapoor, and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, **7**, 98.
10. P. N. Kapoor, and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1966, **10**, 66.
11. V. D. Gupta, and R. C. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 537.
12. F. A. Cotton, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1960, **2**, 325.

been suggested in which the coordination to the metal may take place either through the alkoxide oxygen or the carbonyl oxygen of the ester. It may be interesting to mention here that similar to the observations of Mehrotra for aluminium alkoxides, transesterification reactions in ferric alkoxides also appear to be more facile and less sterically hindered than alcoholysis reactions; this appears to indicate coordination through carbonyl oxygen.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric isopropoxide was prepared as described earlier^{13,14}. The organic esters were prepared by the usual methods¹⁵ and were dried carefully over anhydrous sodium sulphate and purified by careful fractionation. Phenylacetate was distilled before use. Cyclohexane was refluxed over metallic sodium and fractionated before use (b.p. 80.7°)

All glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

Iron was estimated as Fe_2O_3 . The isopropoxy group was estimated by oxidation with normal dichromate¹⁶.

REACTIONS

(1) *Reaction between ferric isopropoxide and tertiary butylacetate*: Tertiary butylacetate (50.0 g.) was added to ferric isopropoxide (4.85 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed under a column at a bath temperature of 130-140°. About 3 ml. of the distillate (isopropylacetate) was collected between 86-90°, after about one hour. Then the temperature of distilling liquid rose to 94° and refluxing was continued and again 15 ml. of the distillate was collected from 94-96°. The remaining tertiary butylacetate was then distilled at a high reflux ratio to bring the reaction to completion. After cooling, excess of tertiary butylacetate was removed under reduced pressure and a brown product (5.7 g.) soluble in benzene was obtained, which sublimed at 145°/0.5 mm. Found: Fe, 20.38%. Calc. for $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU})_3$: Fe, 20.3%.

(2) *Reaction between ferric isopropoxide and normal pentylacetate*: Normal pentylacetate (24.0 g.) was added to a cyclohexane (42.0 g.) solution of ferric isopropoxide (2.83 g.). The contents were refluxed under a fractionating column. After one hour, the azeotrope of isopropylacetate and cyclohexane was collected at 79-80°. The excess of the cyclohexane was distilled out at 80-81°. The rest of the solvent was distilled out under reduced pressure at a bath temperature of 80-90°. A highly viscous brown liquid (3.72 g.) soluble in benzene was thus obtained. Found: Fe, 17.79%. Calc. for $\text{Fe}(\text{OAm})_3$: Fe, 17.60%.

For brevity the results obtained in other reactions are summarised in table 1.

13. P. P. Sharma and R. C. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 74.

14. P. P. Sharma, Ph. D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1966.

15. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry," 1958, p. 382.

16. D. C. Bradley, F. M. A. Halim and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

TABLE 1

Reactions of ferric isopropoxide with organic esters

Fe(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (g)	Organic esters	Cyclo- hexane	Product and state	b.p. (°C/mm)	Iron analysis	
					Found %	Calc. %
3.60	<i>n</i> -butylacetate (25 g)	80 g.	Fe (OBu ⁿ) ₃ highly viscous liquid, soluble in benzene (4.1 g.)	—	20.40	20.30
2.20	<i>iso</i> -butylacetate (14 g)	55 g.	Fe (OBu ⁱ) ₃ brown solid, soluble in benzene (2.5 g)	*Sublimes at 170-180°/0.5 mm.	20.27	20.30
2.00	<i>sec</i> -butylacetate (35 g)	—	Fe (OBu ^s) ₃ brown solid, soluble in benzene (2.3 g.)	*Sublimes at 160-165°/0.5 mm	20.42	20.30
4.85	<i>tert</i> -butylacetate (50 g)	—	Fe (OBu ^t) ₃ brown solid, soluble in benzene (5.7 g)	*Sublimes at 145°/0.5mm	20.38	20.30
2.83	<i>n</i> -pentylacetate (24 g)	42 g.	Fe (OAm ⁿ) ₃ highly viscous liquid, soluble in benzene(3.7 g)	—	17.79	17.60
2.50	phenylacetate (20 g)	60 g	Fe (OPh) ₃ bluish-black solid, in- soluble in benzene (3.5 g)	—	16.75	16.67

*Sublimation at bath temperature.

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